

Donor Properties of 1-Amidino-O-Alkylurea: Part XIII. Biguanide Bis 1-Amidino-O-Alkylurea Cobalt(III) and Hetero 1-Amidino-O-Alkylurea Cobalt(III) Complexes

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Biguanide reacts with trans diammine bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt (III) on a steam bath to furnish the heterochelate, biguanide bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt (III). Characterisation has been made on the basis of conductance and equivalent weights. The complexes exhibit two usual ligand field bands.

The complex, biguanide bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt (III) has been resolved through the fractionation of the d-camphor-10-sulphonate salt. Only the pure levo isomer could be isolated. The rotation characteristics are:

(a) $1[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{AMUH})_2](\text{CS})_3 [\text{M}]_D^{25} = -2174^\circ$.

(b) $1[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{AMUH})_2] \text{I}_3 [\text{M}]_D^{25} = -1930^\circ$.

where BigH = a molecule of biguanide, AMUH = 1-amidino-O-methylurea and CSH = d-camphor-10-sulphonic acid.

Besides the above complexes, a number of hetero 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) compounds have also been synthesised and adequately characterised.

This communication is an immediate extension of our earlier studies concerning the heterochelates of bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt (III)¹. Using ortho-phenanthroline, 2-2'-dipyridyl, ethylenediamine and glycine, heterochelates were synthesised which were found to have unusually high solubility. This was a positive deterrent to any attempt towards resolving the complexes into optical isomers.

On trying biguanide as the third bidentate around cobalt(III), we observed that the solubility of the resulting heterochelates was very much lowered and narrowed down to a range where attempts towards resolving the complex might reasonably materialise. We report herein such complexes. Our choice fell on biguanide because of a very close relationship that exists between biguanide and the 1-amidino-O-alkylurea as co-ordinating ligands^{2,3}.

On warming an aqueous solution of the trans diammine bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) with biguanide there occurs evolution of ammonia and on neutralisation with dilute sulphuric acid, biguanide bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) sulphate crystallises. This can be readily purified from hot water. Double decomposition and other metathetic reactions provide a number of salts, such as the chloride, iodide, cobaltinitrite and d-camphor-10-sulphonate. No pure d-tartrate salt could be isolated. The complexes have

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1. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *This Journal*, this series, Part XII.

2. P. Rây, *Chem. Revs.*, 1961, **61**, 313.

3. R. L. Dutta and P. Rây, *This Journal*, 1959, **36**, 499, 569, 576; R. L. Dutta, *This Journal*, 1960, **37**, 499; R. L. Dutta, B. Sur and N. R. Sengupta, *This Journal*, 1960, **37**, 565, 573; R. L. Dutta and S. Lahiry, *This Journal*, 1961, **38**, 689, 789; 1963, **40**, 863; R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *This Journal*, 1968, **45**, 115, 127, 138.

all been adequately characterised through elemental analyses, conductance measurements, equivalent weight determinations as also electronic absorption spectral measurements. Conductance values place the ions as tri-univalent electrolytes⁴. Equivalent weights are in conformity with the conductance results. Absorption spectra show two ligand field bands typical of cobalt (III) complexes. A comparison drawn from other comparable complexes, (for instance, tris biguanide cobalt(III) shows a closeness in the ligand field strength of biguanide and the 1-amidino-O-alkylureas.

Fractional crystallisation of an aqueous solution of biguanide bis 1 amidino O methylurea cobalt(III) camphor sulphonate furnished first two crops (about 10%), giving a constant levo rotation ($[\alpha]_D^{36} = -200^\circ$; $[M]_D^{36} = -2174^\circ$). Thereafter the crops gave very poor levo rotation, followed by very poor dextro rotation. These fractions proved extremely difficult to purify. The first two crops, however, retained their levo rotation unchanged on further purification, proving that these are the pure levo gyrrates. Trituration of the diastereoisomer with saturated KI gives the complex iodide which was levo rotatory and furnished comparable molar rotation value ($[\alpha]_D^{25} = -250^\circ 25$; $[M]_D^{25} = -1930^\circ$). The

TABLE I

Equivalent weight values

Complex	Found	Required*
1. [Co (BigH) (AMUH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} · 3H ₂ O	192	196
2. [Co (BigH) (AEUH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5}	192	187
3. [Co (AEUH) (AMUH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} · 2H ₂ O	205	200
4. [Co (AEUH) (AMUH) ₂] I ₃ H ₂ O	265	272

where AMUH=1-amidino-O-methylurea; AEUH=1-amidino-O-ethylurea; BigH=biguanide.

*These values have been deduced on the basis of elemental analysis and conductance measurements.

TABLE II

Electrolytic conductance measurements at 33°

Complex	Dilution (litres)	64	128	256	512	1024
		Λ^v	118.0	127.0	134.0	144.5
		$\Lambda \propto^*$	148.6	150.3	151.3	158.7
		$\Lambda \propto$ (mean)	155.9 mhos			
			$\Lambda_M = 461.7$ mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹			
			Equivalent conductance at infinite dilution $\Lambda \propto$ (mean), mhos	Molar conductance Λ_M , mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹		
(b) [Co (BigH) (AMUH) ₂] I ₃			155.8	467.4		
2. [Co (BigH) (AEUH) ₂] Cl ₃			152.3	456.9		
3. [Co (AEUH) (AMUH) ₂] I ₃ H ₂ O			157.4	472.2		

* $\Lambda \propto$ was calculated from Λ^v from Walden formula

$$\Lambda \propto = \Lambda^v (1 + 0.692 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times v^{-\frac{1}{2}})$$

where n_1 is the valency of the cation and n_2 is the valency of the anion.

$$\dagger [M]_D^{25} = \frac{[\alpha]_D^{25} \times \text{molecular weight}}{100}$$

4. M. M. Jones, "Elementary Coordination Chemistry", Prentice Hall, 1964, p-254.

TABLE III

Electronic absorption spectral values

Complex	Band II		Band I	
	Wave number cm ⁻¹	Molar absorptivity litre mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Wave number cm ⁻¹	Molar absorptivity litre mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
1. [Co (BigH) (AMUH) ₂]I ₃	28,600	219	20,800	229
2. [Co (BigH) (AEUH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5}	{ 29,000- 28,600	143	{ 21,000- 20,800	141
3. [Co (AEUH)(AMUH) ₂] I ₃ H ₂ O	{ 27,800- 27,400	330	{ 20,800- 20,600	234
4. [Co (BigH) ₃](SO ₄) _{1.5} 3.5 H ₂ O	28.600	187	{ 21,000- 20,800	207

diastereoisomer as also the pure levo rotatory iodide salts are quite stable in a aqueous solution at room temperature for days together nor was there any racemisation on heating the samples in the solid crystalline forms. Above resolutions have been duplicated at least three times with similar results Fractional crystallisation of the d-camphor-10-sulphonate of the corresponding heterochelate of the O-ethylurea derivative gave fractions with poor rotation values, which on repeated fractionation gave in very poor yield a crop with $[\alpha]_D^{36} = -170^\circ$. Thus in this series of mono biguanide bis l amidino-O alkylurea cobalt (III) complexes, only the pure levo rotatory isomer has been located in poor yield. However, there was found no evidence for asymmetric transformation of the second order.

The action of a l-amidino-O-alkylurea on the trans diammine bis l-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) releases ammonia on warming thus producing a smooth route to the synthesis of hitherto unknown hetero l-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) complexes. These are interesting examples of one and the same coordination zone around cobalt(III) having differently substituted l-amidino-O-alkylureas. Parallel instances have also been reported for biguanide complexes of cobalt(III)⁵. The complexes are highly soluble, so that we felt discouraged to undertake any worthwhile attempts towards resolving the complexes into optical antipodes.

TABLE IV

Comparison of $[\alpha]_D^t$ and $[M]_D^t$ values of related complexes

Complex	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$	Temp. °C	References
1. l[Co(BigH) ₃] (SO ₄) _{1.5} aq.	-362.5°	-2062°	31	Ray & Dutt (loc. cit).
2. l[Co (BigH) (AMUH) ₂] I ₃	-250°	-1930°	25	This research
3. l[Co (AMUH) (BigH) ₂] (SO ₄) _{1.5} H ₂ O	-408°	-2338°	25	Dutta & Syamal (loc. cit).

5. R. L. Dutta and S. Sarkar, *Science & Culture*, 1964, **30**, 549; *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 842.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-amidino-O-methylurea and 1-amidino-ethylurea sulphates were prepared according to the published method³. trans-diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate and chloride and trans diammine bis 1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) sulphate were prepared as described earlier⁶. Biguanide acid sulphate was prepared according to the published procedure⁷.

Biguanidobis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate. trans diammine bis 1 amidino-O-methylurea cobalt (III) mono sulphate(1g) in water (15 ml) and neutralised biguanide acid sulphate (0.56 g) were mixed and heated on a steam bath until the evolution of ammonia ceased. The mixture was cooled, neutralised with 2N H₂SO₄ and allowed to cool for half an hour. The rose red crystals separated were filtered and recrystallised from hot water and finally washed with spirit and dried in air. The substance is soluble in water, insoluble in alcohol and acetone. {Found. Co, 10.1 ; N, 30.9, SO₄, 24.6; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 9.6. [Co (BigH) (AMUH)₂] (SO₄)_{1.5}. 3H₂O requires Co, 10.0 ; N, 30.9; SO₄, 24.4; H₂O, 9.1%}.

Biguanido bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) chloride. trans diammine bis amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) mono chloride (1 g) in water (15 ml) was mixed with neutralised biguanide chloride (1:1 ratio) and heated on a steam bath. Ammonia was disengaged ; the mixture was heated until the evolution of ammonia ceased. The mixture was then cooled, neutralised with 2N HCl and evaporated on a steam bath to a small volume. The solution was then cooled in ice to give orange crystals, which were filtered, washed with spirit and dried in a desiccator. The substance is soluble in water, insoluble in alcohol and acetone. {Found: Co, 12.0; N, 36.8 ; Cl, 21.8. [Co(BigH) (AMUH)₂]Cl₃ requires Co, 11.8; N, 36.6; Cl, 21.4%}.

The iodide, bromide and d-camphor-10-sulphonate salts were prepared as crystalline products by the reaction of the chloride with a concentrated solution of KI, KBr or neutralised d-camphor-10-sulphonic acid as the case may be and cooling the mixture in ice bath. Analysis and physical properties of these complexes are included in Table V.

(-) *Biguanido bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) (+) camphor sulphonate.* The racemic salt(5 g), obtained as above, was dissolved in water(225 ml) and allowed to evaporate at room temperature under a fan. The first two crops of crystals (0.5 g) separating were found to be levo rotatory. The other fractions were also levo rotatory but the optical rotations were found to be lowered. A solid sample heated at 120° for 1 hr, did not show any appreciable change in rotation in solution. An aqueous solution of the sample also remained optically stable for a week. But the solid sample showed tendency of racemisation on keeping for months. An aqueous solution left for 12 hr. at 55° also racemised completely to a zero rotation. {Found: Co 5.3; N 16.9. [Co (BigH) (AMUH)₂] (CS)₃ requires Co 5.4; N 16.7%}. (α)_D³⁶ = -200°; (M)_D³⁶ = -2174°.

(-) *Biguanido bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) iodide:* The levo gyrrate of the (+) camphor sulphonate was triturated in a mortar with a saturated solution of KI and allowed to stand for half an hour. The crystals separated were filtered, washed with ice

6. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, *This Journal*, this series, Part. IX, 1968, 45, 115.

7. W. C. Fernelius, *Inorganic Synthesis*, McGraw-Hill Book Company, Vol. VII, p. 75.

cold water and dried in air. An aqueous solution of the sample remained optically stable for a week. {Found: N, 23.6; I, 49.7. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{I}_3$, requires N 23.5; I, 49.3%}. $(\alpha)_D^{25} = -250^\circ$; $(M)_D^{25} = -1930^\circ$.

Biguanido bis 1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) sulphate (Orange). Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) sulphate (1 g) in water (15 ml) and neutralised biguanide acid sulphate (0.6 g) were mixed and heated on a steam bath until all the ammonia were evolved. This was then treated as for the methyl derivative. This is soluble in water, insoluble in alcohol and acetone. {Found: Co, 10.2; N, 32.5; SO_4 , 25.8. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{AEUH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5}$ requires Co, 10.4; N, 32.3; SO_4 , 25.5%}.

Biguanido bis 1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) chloride was prepared as orange crystals by double decomposition of the sulphate with BaCl_2 and then concentrating the filtrate followed by cooling in ice. The substance is soluble in water, insoluble in alcohol and acetone. {Found: Co, 11.4; N, 34.9; Cl, 20.5. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{Cl}_3$ requires Co, 11.2; N, 34.6; Cl, 20.2%}.

The iodide and bromide salts were prepared as crystalline products by metathetic reaction of the chloride with that of a concentrated solution of KI, KBr respectively and then cooling in ice bath. These were all dried in air and included in Table V.

Biguanido bis-1-amidino-O-ethylurea cobalt(III) d-camphor-10-sulphonate was obtained as orange crystals by double decomposition of the chloride with neutralised d-camphor-10-sulphonic acid. This is soluble in water and alcohol, insoluble in acetone. {Found: Co, 5.3; N, 16.5. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{AEUH})_2](\text{CS})_3$ requires Co, 5.2; N, 16.3%}. An attempt to resolve the compound by slow process of crystallisation produced levo isomer as the less soluble fraction with $[\alpha]_D^{36} = -40^\circ$ only. This was repeatedly fractionated till a very small fraction with $[\alpha]_D^{36} = -170^\circ$ was finally obtained. However, the overall yield being much poorer compared to the O-methylurea complex, we did not attempt preparation of the iodide salt.

1-amidino-O-ethylurea bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate: Diammine bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea cobalt(III) sulphate (1 g) and 1-amidino-O-ethylurea sulphate (0.48 g) were mixed with water (15 ml) and heated on a steam bath until evolution of ammonia ceased. The mixture was then cooled, neutralised with 2N H_2SO_4 and scratched repeatedly with acetone to give rose red crystals, which were filtered and dried in a desiccator. The substance is soluble in water, insoluble in alcohol and acetone. {Found: Co, 9.8; N, 27.6; SO_4 , 24.6. $[\text{Co}(\text{AEUH})(\text{AMUH})_2](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 9.8; N, 27.9; SO_4 , 24.0%}.

The chloride salt was prepared by double decomposition of the sulphate with BaCl_2 , concentrating the filtrate and subsequent cooling. The iodide salt was prepared by metathetic reaction of the chloride with KI and then cooling in ice.

All the cobaltinitrite salts were prepared by double decomposition of the sulphate salt with a concentrated solution of $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$.

Analytical methods: The experimental procedure as described in Part IX was followed here.

TABLE V

Analysis, Colour and Solubility of Cobalt(III) Heterochelates

Complex	Colour	Analytical results				Solubility
		Co %	N %	Anion H ₂ O*		
[Co (BigH) (AMUH) ₂]Br ₃	Orange	Found: 9.5 Reqd: 9.3	29.0 28.8	38.5 38.0	—	water
[Co (BigH) (AMUH) ₂]I ₃	Orange	Found: 7.8 Reqd: 7.6	23.7 23.5	49.7 49.3	—	water, alcohol
[Co (BigH) (AMUH) ₂] [Co (NO ₂) ₆]	Yellow	Found: 15.4 Reqd: 15.3	34.2 3.45	—	—	water
[Co (BigH) (AMUH) ₂] (CS) ₃ **	Orange red	Found: 5.2 Reqd: 5.4	16.9 16.7	—	—	water, alcohol
[Co (BigH) (AEUH) ₂]I ₃	Orange	Found: 7.6 Reqd: 7.3	23.0 22.7	47.3 47.6	—	water, alcohol
[Co (BigH) (AEUH) ₂]Br ₃	Orange	Found: 9.0 Reqd: 8.9	27.4 27.6	36.6 36.4	—	water
[Co (BigH) (AEUH) ₂] [Co (NO ₂) ₆]	Yellow	Found: 15.8 Reqd: 15.6	35.5 35.2	—	—	water
[Co (AEUH) (AMUH) ₂] Cl ₃	Orange	Found: 11.3 Reqd: 11.1	32.0 31.8	20.6 20.2	—	water
[Co (AEUH)(AMUH) ₂]I ₃ H ₂ O	Orange	Found: 7.3 Reqd: 7.1	20.7 20.4	46.7 46.4	—	water, alcohol
[Co (AEUH) (AMUH) ₂] [Co (NO ₂) ₆] H ₂ O	Yellow	Found: 15.3 Reqd: 15.3	32.6 32.5	—	2.4 2.3	water

*By loss at 110°

**[α]_D³⁶ = -25°

Optical rotation measurements were made in a Carl Zeiss student model Polarimeter of limited accuracy ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) using 0.2% aqueous solution of the complex salts.

This is a pleasure to acknowledge our indebtedness to C.S.I.R. for financial assistance to one of us (A.S.). We express our gratitude to Prof. Santi Ranjan Palit for his interest in our scheme. We also thank Prof. S. K. Siddhanta for the encouragement given us. We gratefully acknowledge the generous gift of dicyandiamide by the American Cyanamide Company.